

ANTECEDENTS AND CONSEQUENCES OF ONLINE IMPULSE BUYING

ANDRIANI NATASHA PUTRI ^{1*} and INDIRA RACHMAWATI ²

^{1,2} Faculty of Economics and Business, Telkom University, Bandung, Indonesia.

* Corresponding Author Email: andrianinatasha@gmail.com

Abstract

The practicality of shopping through social commerce makes consumers vulnerable to being tempted to shop impulsely without considering the consequences carefully. Thus, it tends to cause post-purchase dissonance. Since there is only a few studies scrutinizing factors affecting impulse buying and the simultaneous effects, this study aimed to discover and understand the primary factors of online impulse purchase among social commerce buyers, particularly in TikTok Shop in Indonesia and the impulse buying effects on post-purchase dissonance. The primary factors of impulse buying examined in this study include sales promotion, shopping lifestyle, social factor, and positive emotion. This quantitative study was conducted by distributing questionnaires on 251 samples selected using the purposive sampling technique. A SEM analysis was employed using the SmartPLS software. The study results demonstrate that sales promotion, shopping lifestyle, social factor, and positive emotion positively and significantly affected impulse buying. The most dominant factor was positive emotion. Furthermore, the study also proved that impulse buying positively and significantly affected post-purchase dissonance experienced by TikTok Shop consumers.

Keywords: Online Impulse Buying, Post Purchase Dissonance, Sales Promotion, Shopping Lifestyle, Social Factor.

INTRODUCTION

Today, social media is not only used to extend connections and share experiences but also acts as product trading media. This phenomenon is called social commerce. Social commerce is a process of buying and selling goods and services conducted directly on social media platforms. This social commerce phenomenon is considered the new competitor of popular e-commerce platforms, such as Shopee, Bukalapak, Lazada, and Tokopedia. A report by McKinsey stated that 40% of Indonesian e-commerce market was dominated by social commerce (Sirlo, 2020). Based on data of Statista in 2023, the gross merchandise value (GMV) of Indonesian social commerce is estimated to reach approximately 8.2 billion US dollar. This value is estimated to triple, achieving 22.1 billion US dollar in 2028. It shows a massive opportunity for entrepreneurs in utilizing social commerce platforms. TikTok Shop becomes the most popular social commerce among online customers. It is shown by the Indonesian TikTok users reaching 109.9 million and ranked second globally after the United States (US) with 113.25 million in February 2023. Moreover, based on the latest survey uploaded on the Statista website, TikTok managed to be the most-used social commerce platform by Indonesian consumers in the last 12 months. The role of easy-to-reach online shopping places allowing consumers to shop anytime and anywhere increases impulse buying habits, i.e., the phenomenon of consumers making purchasing decisions for products that were not actually planned. TikTok is the number one application encouraging consumers to purchase. Consumer expenditure increased to 77%

in TikTok throughout 2021. A total of 67% of TikTok users stated that TikTok encourages them to spend money despite having no plan to shop (Octavilia, 2023).

There are several factors influencing impulse buying. One of which is sales promotion. TikTok Shop is known for having various sales promotions for consumers, starting from free shipping, cashbacks, discounts, free samples, and others. Furthermore, TikTok Shop also celebrates various marketing events, e.g., Mega Sales, FUNtastic payday, twin date sale, Ramadhan Sale, and Ied Sale (Populix, 2023). According to (Chan et al., 2017), sales promotion is the most effective marketing stimulus from marketers to attract consumers in purchasing products. A previous study also mentioned that consumers are more impulsive when the business provides offers or special discounts (Menon et al., 2016). It is proven in the Mega Sales 11.11 campaign in 2022, where TikTok Shop experienced increased GMV to 193% compared to the previous period. The 12.12 GMV in 2022 also experienced growth by 203% (Rahma, 2023). It provides a huge opportunity for marketers to develop strategies that trigger and affect impulse buying (theTradeDesk, 2022).

Along the time, online shopping trend shows changed in shopping behavior of the public. Shopping even becomes the most popular lifestyle for several consumers. Shopping lifestyle encourages a person to allocate time and money to acquire various products during the shopping process (Sari & Hermawati, 2020). The app's popularity makes shopping through TikTok as a new lifestyle for consumers (Kompas.com, 2023). It is marked by the number of TikTok application users that continues to grow, impacting TikTok's revenue. In 2021, TikTok acquired revenue of \$1.09 billion, while its revenue in 2022 increased to \$1.64 billion (Databoks, 2022). Consumer shopping style while on TikTok Shop is that 58% of users tend to search brands and new products on the platform. Then, 71% of users tend to buy products after watching ads in TikTok (Liputan6.com, 2021). Ahmad et al. (2022) asserted that product purchases following latest trends and accidentally found products cause impulse buying. Although a trend can push public interest on a particular brand, not all popular things will do. Another crucial factor that affects impulse buying is social factors. There are several parties playing essential roles in making purchasing decisions, e.g., parents, family members, peers, colleagues, and such (Rahim et al., 2016). Approximately 90% of people will buy products based on a recommendation from friends (Cnnindonesia.com, 2022). More than 68% of respondents considered friend recommendation when selecting brands than following celebrity or influencer recommendations (Cnnindonesia.com, 2022).

The next factor influencing impulse purchase is positive emotion. Shaifali et al. (2021) explained that positive emotion can trigger impulse buying. In generating positive emotions, TikTok Shop arranges the shopenertainment concept. Following this concept, TikTok Shop offers features encouraging users to enjoy entertaining content, then asking them to shop through live stream and short video features. After finishing the purchasing process, consumers will evaluate their purchased products. Due to the practicality of online shopping, consumers are prone to impulse buying without considering the consequences. Therefore, it tends to cause post-purchase dissonance (Chetioui & El Bouzidi, 2023). Upon experiencing dissonance, consumers will feel bad and regret their impulse buying behavior after buying non-essential

products (Chen et al., 2020). This purchase regret occurs when customers appreciate a specific product and finish the purchase, but then are unsure about the product or service quality. Based on a study by Novia (2020), the online shopping regret rate in Indonesia was relatively high. One of the characteristics causing post-purchase dissonance is impulsivity (Chen et al., 2020). Although several studies focused on the benefits of impulse buying, only a few are focused on consumer reactions post-impulse buying (Chen et al., 2020).

Based on this background, the limited studies of impulse buying behavior in social commerce, and the minuscule number of studies examining the relationship between impulse buying and post-purchase dissonance, it is critical to study the matter to allow marketers or businesses to arrange appropriate strategies in encouraging impulse buying behaviour and minimize post-purchase dissonance and regret.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Impulse Buying

In 1987, Rock mentioned that impulse buying occurs when consumers have a sudden continuous urge to buy something immediately (Lazim et al., 2020). Unplanned shopping behavior is to buy instantly without any considerations on the possible benefits or effects. Impulse buying can happen anytime anywhere, without second thoughts, and is plausible to be experienced by all consumers (Kumar et al., 2020). Consumers tend to be interested to a brand or product when they see it (Martaleni et al., 2022). However, it is unfortunate that such products are non-essentials and unthinkable before (Made & Purnama, 2019). Generally, there are four impulse buying types according to Stern (1962), i.e., pure impulse buying, suggestion impulse buying, reminder impulse buying, and planned impulse buying.

Sales Promotion

Sales promotion is an effective strategy to significantly increase sales volume immediately. Sales promotion is defined as a captivating incentive offer for consumers that motivate them to purchase at the time (Kotler & Keller, 2021). Sales promotion is a form of marketing communication in a limited time to add values to a product or brand (Kegan, 2020). A study by Blattberg & Neslin (1993) mentioned four principal objectives of promotion, i.e., improve the shop's image, create traffic, create price image, and empty product stock or inventory. According to Hajjat (2021), the most commonly used sales promotion types are samples, coupons, rebates, price off deals, contests, and lottery. Meanwhile, Evans (2019) argued that sales promotion oriented towards consumers that can be used to stimulate sales by consumers are rebates, price packs, promoted products, promotion reach, ads quantity in promotion media, and message delivery quality in the ad in promotion media.

Based on a study by Tran (2019), sales promotions positively influenced consumer impulse buying behavior because people are interested when seeing a cheaper price compared to the normal price. It is supported by Bandyopadhyay et al. (2021), which stated that various sales promotion types offered by companies can encourage impulse purchases.

Therefore, the researcher formulated the following hypothesis:

H1: Sales Promotion has a positive and significant effect on Impulse Buying at TikTok Shop.

Shopping Lifestyle

Hajjat (2021) explained that lifestyle is how the consumer behaves daily in fulfilling their needs by consuming a product based on their interests, activities, opinions, and beliefs. How we shop reflects our status, class, and habits. In an economic perspective, shopping lifestyle shows the way a person allocates their revenue for various products and services and specific alternatives in differentiating similar categories. One will purchase a preferred brand although they do not have enough money (Betty et al., 2006). It is clear that shopping has become a lifestyle for people worldwide and crucial for everyone. Shopping lifestyle is demonstrated in several indicators to discover the relationship between shopping lifestyle and impulse buying. Japariato & Sugiharto (2011) asserted that such indicators are ad offers, latest models, popular brands, best quality, different branded products, and same branded products. Meanwhile, following Aqmala & Putra (2022), shopping lifestyle indicators are ads offers, latest models, popular brands, best quality, and shopping style variations.

Shopping style is an essential factor that will arouse consumer interest in a marketplace. The shopping style as the main reference for consumers in purchasing a product in a particular marketplace will influence consumers' positive emotions, allowing online impulse buying to occur (Aprilia et al., 2022). The hypothesis testing result shows that the shopping lifestyle variable influence impulse buying behavior. It is discovered that the higher the consumer's shopping style, the higher the impulse buying, and vice versa. Respondents stated that shopping style is in the high category since online stores are always the main choice for shopping and made purchases (Aqmala & Putra, 2022). Therefore, the researcher formulated the following hypothesis:

H2: Shopping Lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on Impulse Buying at TikTok Shop.

Social Factor

A study by Pujiastuti et al. (2022) mentioned that the social environment is a place where people interact with each other and do things together with each other and with their environment. It aligns with Aqmala & Putra (2022), stating that social factors are also defined as anything used as a reference in people interactions concerning the society or community. Social factors can be seen from relationships with friends, family, and parents in influencing purchasing decisions. Tran (2019) stated that the presence of other people highly changes a consumer's purchasing behavior positively, especially when they are a couple or for those who have close relationships with family, friends, or co-workers. Consumers often turn to others, especially friends and family members, for opinions about products and services.

Several precedent studies have examined the effect of social factors on impulse buying. A study by Aqmal & Putra (2022) demonstrated that social factors comprising the presence of family, peers, co-workers, and reference groups positively influenced online impulse buying behavior. Furthermore, another conclusion from the previous study mentioned that a colleague's shopping desire and their supporting or refuting view can significantly influence an individual customer's purchase amount (Tran, 2019). Therefore, the researcher formulated the following hypothesis:

H3: Social Factor has a positive and significant effect on Impulse Buying at TikTok Shop

Positive Emotion

Emotion is a complex concept to explain, which is why the definition of emotion should be observed cautiously. Emotion comes in various shapes. In general, emotions are divided into two groups: negative and positive. Positive emotion usually leads to joyful feeling that support individuals to approach stimuli such as happiness, satisfaction, and appreciation (Martaleni et al., 2022). According to Aqmal & Putra (2022), one's positive emotions include interest, sense of comfort, pride, joy, pleasure, satisfaction, affection, admiration, relief, and sense of emotion. Sudarsono (2017) believed that positive emotion can be translated into one's feeling that affect decision-making, which tend to reduce complexity and time in making purchasing decisions. The possibility of positive emotions depends on stimuli offered by a business; hence, influencing consumers' emotions or feelings (Soodan & Pandey, 2016).

With the internet development and the shift in consumer behavior from traditional to online purchasing, marketers need to understand the role of emotions in triggering unplanned purchases in the digital environment (Zheng et al., 2020). A previous study examining emotions in marketing found that emotions play a vital role in triggering impulse purchases (He et al., 2018). According to Fu et al. (2018), consumer emotions affect one's tendency to have unplanned purchases. Consumers having positive emotions will more likely be involved in approaching than rejecting behavior. Positive emotions can appear from fulfilled needs or wants from such a person. Positive emotions can trigger unplanned purchases due to joyful feelings influenced by various environments encouraging such purchases. Therefore, the researcher formulated the following hypothesis:

H4: Positive Emotion has a positive and significant effect on Impulse Buying at TikTok Shop.

Post Purchase Dissonance

Kotler & Keller (2021) stated that post-purchase is the fifth stage of a purchasing process. In this stage, consumers evaluate whether the selected alternatives can fulfil the needs and expectations. In 1957, cognitive dissonance was coined by Festinger as discomfort occurring when there is a non-conformity between one's belief and confusing outcomes (Chetioui & El Bouzidi, 2023). Referring to the Cognitive Dissonance Theory, dissonance or discomfort appears when consumers have a controversial thought on their belief or attitude on a particular object (Lazim et al., 2020). Consumers tend to believe that they make a great choice. However,

upon buying products or goods without a plan (unplanned purchase), it might confront their previous belief regarding the decision-making ability. Thus, creating post-purchase dissonance (Sameeni et al., 2022). Regarding the impulsive buying behavior, a consumer committing impulse buying tends to have post-purchase dissonance. It is caused by the absence of logical explanation for their purchase, causing discomfort that leads to post-purchase dissonance (Barta et al., 2022). Impulse buying creates more dissonance than planned buying (Hasan Usma, 2014). Instead of having a positive influence, impulse buying rather has a negative impact on consumer satisfaction (Suyanto & Femi, 2023). Study results by Chetioui & El Bouzidi (2023) stated that impulse buying has a positive relationship on post-purchase dissonance. A similar opinion is conveyed by Chen et al. (2020), stating that impulse buying directly and positively affected product dissonance and emotion dissonance of consumers. Following Shan et al. (2020), since impulse buying is unplanned with a little to no cognition, consumers often feel regret. It is caused by the lack of information search effort in making decisions due to emotional elements dominating rational elements (Lazim et al., 2020). Therefore, the researcher formulated the following hypothesis:

H5: Impulse Buying has a positive and significant effect on Post Purchase Dissonance at TikTok Shop.

Referring to the results of previous researches and the hypotheses that have been developed, then research model is created as depicted in the following:

Figure 1: Research Framework

METHODOLOGY

Data Collection, Measurement, and Sample

The study population was users of TikTok in Indonesia. The sampling technique used in this study was non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling method. Purposive sampling is a sample determination technique by selecting subjects based on certain criteria instead of strata, random, or area (Hikmawati, 2017:68). The sample criteria:

1. TikTok application user;
2. Domiciled in Indonesia;
3. Ever purchased a product through the TikTok Shop (at least once).

Since the study population size is unknown and uncertain, the researchers used a special PLS-SEM sample formula proposed by Hair Jr. et al. (2021:17) as follows:

$$Significance = 1\%: n_{min} > \left(\frac{3.168}{p_{min}}\right)^2 (1)$$

Thus, based on the calculation result, the minimum sample size in this study was 251 respondents. Data collection technique was using a questionnaire in Google Form. The first part lists the respondents' gender, age, and frequency of shopping. The second part consists of measuring each variable such as sales promotion, shopping lifestyle, social factor, positive emotions, impulse buying, and post purchase dissonance.

Measurements and Survey Instruments

The items were borrowed from the previously conducted studies that were considered relevant for construct measurement and were designed in Indonesian. Sales promotion and were measured with six items adapted from Aqmala & Putra (2022). Shopping Lifestyle was assessed with six items borrowed from Cobb & Hoyer (1986). Social Factor was measured through three items adapted from Aqmala & Putra (2022). For positive emotion and impulse buying positive emotion and impulse buying with each of the four question items were also taken by Aqmala & Putra (2022). Meanwhile, post-purchase dissonance was measured using four items adapted from Chetioui & El Bouzidi (2023).

The respondents' demographic characteristics consist of 67% of the respondents or 168 people were female, while 33% or 83 people were male. Based on age, 135 people or 54% were 19-24 years old. Then 32% were 13-18 years old, 12% were 25-30 years old and 5 or 2% were over 30 years old. Based on the frequency of shopping in one month, 75 people, or 30% of the respondents, shop twice in a month. Then, 70 other people shop three times a month. 53 people, or 21%, shop online once a month, while 51 people, or the other 21%, and shop as many as four times or even more in a monthly period.

Table 1: Respondent’s Demographic Attributes

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	168	67%
	Female	83	33%
Age	13-18 years old	81	54%
	19-24 years old	135	32%
	25-30 years old	30	12%
	>30 years old	5	2%
Frequency of Shopping	Once a month	53	21%
	Twice a month	75	30%
	Three times a month	70	28%
	Four times or more a month	53	21%

Source: Result of Data Processing (2023).

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Regarding the causal study approach used, this study aimed to analyze the relationship and the influence of each variable. In achieving the study objectives, the researchers used structural equation model (SEM) analysis. Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a multivariate statistical analysis method to predict and to explain one or more dependent variables and test the relationship between variables in a model, both between indicators and their constructs or the relationship between constructs (Hamid and Anwar, 2017). In general, SEM is divided into two, i.e., covariance-based SEM (CB-SEM) and partial least path modeling (PLS-SEM). In this study, the SEM type used was PLS-SEM. PLS is used to explain whether there is a relationship between latent variables and test the truth of a theory (Ghozali, 2021:5).

In PLS-SEM, there are two stages of evaluating the measurement model used, i.e., the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model). The measurement model evaluation stage aims to measure the validity and reliability values of a model. Construct validity testing in PLS-SEM consists of convergent and discriminant validity. Loading factor and AVE indicators of more than 0.50 are used as criteria for accepting convergent validity, meanwhile, the Cross Loading, Fornell Lackrer, and HTMT values are the acceptance criteria for the discriminant validity test. In reliability testing, measuring the reliability of a construct with reflective indicators can be performed using two methods: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability. The Cronbach's Alpha and Composite reliability values of the variables must be ≥ 0.70 (Ghozali, 2021:70).

A structural model aims to show the estimation strength between latent variables (Ghozali, 2021:7). There are several item components as the criteria for assessing the structural model (inner model), i.e., R-Square, Q-Square, F-Square Path Coefficient, and Model Fit values (Ghozali & Latan, 2017:78). To prove the relationship between variables, it is necessary to test the hypothesis (Indrawati, 2015). Hypothesis refers to a temporary answer to the research problem formulation. It is called a temporary answer since the answer is only based on existing theory instead of empirical facts obtained through the data collection process (Hikmawati,

2017:57). A hypothesis test can be accepted or rejected by considering the significance value shown between variables, i.e., t-value and p-value. Since the study used a one-tailed hypothesis testing, the hypothesis test used a 5% significance level or $p = 0.05$ (Hikmawati, 2017:52). The path coefficient value from t-statistics on a 0.05 significance level must be over 1.65.

Measuring Outer Model

Table 2: Convergent Validity

Construct	Indicator	Loading Factor	AVE	Conclusion
Sales Promotion	SP1	0.788	0.649	Valid
	SP2	0.806		
	SP3	0.802		
	SP4	0.823		
	SP5	0.809		
	SP6	0.806		
Shopping Lifestyle	SL1	0.801	0.635	Valid
	SL2	0.791		
	SL3	0.793		
	SL4	0.812		
	SL5	0.804		
	SL6	0.778		
Social Factor	SF1	0.822	0.665	Valid
	SF2	0.832		
	SF3	0.838		
	SF4	0.789		
	SF5	0.795		
Positive Emotion	PE1	0.836	0.694	Valid
	PE2	0.841		
	PE3	0.829		
	PE4	0.828		
Impulse Buying	IMB1	0.806	0.698	Valid
	IMB2	0.855		
	IMB3	0.848		
	IMB4	0.831		
Post purchase Dissonance	PPR1	0.815	0.641	Valid
	PPR2	0.800		
	PPR3	0.815		
	PPR4	0.771		

Source: Result of Data Processing (2023).

All items in this study questionnaire could be extracted perfectly with a loading factor value of > 0.5 . Also, an indicator is stated valid and meet the criteria if the AVE value is > 0.5 (Ghozali, 2021:68). Based on Table 2, each variable has loading factor and AVE values of > 0.5 thus, all study variables are valid and meeting the convergent validity test requirements. This shows that the items used in this study could explain the construct and its latent variables well.

Table 3: Cross Loading Factor

Indicator	Online Impulse Buying	Positive Emotion	Post-Purchased Dissonance	Social Factor	Shopping Lifestyle	Sales Promotion
IMB1	0.806	0.652	0.668	0.571	0.636	0.575
IMB2	0.855	0.635	0.598	0.602	0.645	0.589
IMB3	0.848	0.590	0.628	0.587	0.621	0.547
IMB4	0.831	0.601	0.596	0.608	0.606	0.529
PE1	0.588	0.836	0.583	0.565	0.619	0.609
PE2	0.617	0.841	0.612	0.611	0.647	0.554
PE3	0.644	0.829	0.595	0.602	0.612	0.605
PE4	0.625	0.828	0.606	0.608	0.640	0.558
PPR1	0.648	0.596	0.815	0.580	0.599	0.590
PPR2	0.585	0.514	0.800	0.534	0.553	0.554
PPR3	0.642	0.616	0.815	0.574	0.622	0.609
PPR4	0.495	0.575	0.771	0.446	0.540	0.583
SF1	0.548	0.623	0.549	0.822	0.610	0.558
SF2	0.590	0.609	0.555	0.832	0.656	0.546
SF3	0.598	0.561	0.536	0.838	0.643	0.479
SF4	0.546	0.573	0.520	0.789	0.568	0.524
SF5	0.607	0.552	0.577	0.795	0.626	0.492
SL1	0.543	0.608	0.548	0.635	0.801	0.536
SL2	0.600	0.591	0.531	0.596	0.791	0.574
SL3	0.650	0.554	0.580	0.616	0.793	0.577
SL4	0.613	0.605	0.594	0.558	0.812	0.578
SL5	0.579	0.642	0.626	0.632	0.804	0.638
SL6	0.605	0.611	0.582	0.605	0.778	0.569
SP1	0.543	0.542	0.573	0.521	0.539	0.788
SP2	0.548	0.558	0.591	0.489	0.574	0.806
SP3	0.507	0.583	0.587	0.536	0.552	0.802
SP4	0.553	0.602	0.583	0.507	0.626	0.823
SP5	0.514	0.543	0.574	0.476	0.577	0.809
SP6	0.578	0.541	0.615	0.552	0.643	0.806

Source: Result of Data Processing (2023).

Table 3 shows that each cross-loading value of a construct is higher than the construct loading value against other constructs. This shows that all indicators have high discriminant validity. Then, a Fornell-Larcker Criterion test was performed, where the square root of AVE for each variable is higher than the correlation value among variables. The following Table is the result of the Fornell Lackrer test:

Table 4: Fornell-Lackrer

Indicator	Online Impulse Buying	Positive Emotion	Post-Purchased Dissonance	Sales Promotion	Shopping Lifestyle	Social Factor
Online Impulse Buying	0.835					
Positive Emotion	0.743	0.833				
Post purchase Dissonance	0.747	0.719	0.801			
Sales Promotion	0.671	0.697	0.729	0.806		
Shopping Lifestyle	0.752	0.756	0.725	0.727	0.797	
Social Factor	0.709	0.716	0.672	0.638	0.762	0.815

Source: Result of Data Processing (2023).

Table 4 reveals that each tested variable has fulfilled the discriminant validity requirement since each square root of AVE shows a higher value than correlation among variables. Besides the Fornell-Leckrer Criterion test, the next discriminant validity test is examining the HTMT value. According to Ghozali (2021), The HTMT value must be <0.9 to be declared discriminantly valid. The following Table is the result of the HTMT test:

Table 5: HTMT

Indicator	Online Impulse Buying	Positive Emotion	Post-Purchased Dissonance	Sales Promotion	Shopping Lifestyle	Social Factor
Online Impulse Buying						
Positive Emotion	0.868					
Post purchase Dissonance	0.885	0.861				
Sales Promotion	0.767	0.799	0.855			
Shopping Lifestyle	0.863	0.869	0.850	0.817		
Social Factor	0.820	0.828	0.789	0.722	0.866	

Source: Result of Data Processing (2023).

Based on Table 5, all variables on this study have HTMT values more than 0.9. Therefore, each variable is discriminantly valid.

Table 6: Reliability Test

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha (> 0,6)	Composite Reliability (> 0,6)	Conclusion
Sales Promotion	0.892	0.917	Reliable
Shopping Lifestyle	0.885	0.912	Reliable
Social Factor	0.874	0.908	Reliable
Positive Emotion	0.853	0.901	Reliable
Online Impulse Buying	0.855	0.902	Reliable
Post-Purchased Dissonance	0.814	0.877	Reliable

Source: Result of Data Processing (2023).

Furthermore, Table 6 shows that, based on the Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability values. All variables are declared reliable since they have Composite Reliability values over 0.7 and Cronbach's Alpha values over 0.6.

Measuring Inner Model

In testing the inner model, the R-Square value or coefficient of determination measures how much the endogenous construct can be explained by the exogenous construct. The R-Square value range is divided into three: 0.75 (strong), 0.50 (moderate), and 0.25 (weak) (Ghozali, 2021:73). The R-Square test yielded the following findings:

Table 7: R-Square

Variable	R-square	Adjusted R-square
Online Impulse Buying	0.661	0.655
Positive Emotion	0.650	0.645
Post-Purchased Dissonance	0.557	0.556

Source: Result of Data Processing (2023).

Online Impulse Buying variable is 0.661. It means that the influence of the Sales Promotion, Shopping Lifestyle, Social Factor, and Positive Emotion variables on Online Impulse Buying is 66.1%. Furthermore, the R-Square value for the Positive Emotion variable is 0.650. It indicates that the influence exerted by the Sales Promotion, Shopping Lifestyle, and Social Factor variables on Positive Emotion is 65.0%. Meanwhile, the R-Square value of the Post-Purchased Dissonance variable is 0.557, indicating that the influence of the Online Impulse Buying variable on Post-Purchased Dissonance is 55.7%.

The path coefficient value in structural testing shows the positive or negative direction of the variable and shows the level of significance in hypothesis testing. The path coefficient test yielded the following findings:

Table 8: Path Coefficient

Jalur	Path Coefficient
Sales Promotion -> Online Impulse Buying	0.137
Shopping Lifestyle -> Online Impulse Buying	0.278
Social Factor -> Online Impulse Buying	0.198
Positive Emotion -> Online Impulse Buying	0.296
Online Impulse Buying -> Post-Purchased Dissonance	0.747

Source: Result of Data Processing (2023).

Table 8 shows that the path coefficient value of independent variables with the highest value in influencing impulse buying is positive emotion by 0.296. Meanwhile, the variable with the lowest influence value is sales promotion with by 0.137. Furthermore, the impact of impulse buying on post-purchased dissonance is 0.747. The inner model testing also conducted Predictive Relevance (Q^2) calculation. If the Q^2 value is less than 0, the model is considered having poor predictive relevance.

The Q Square test results are shown below:

Table 9: Q-square Predictive

Variable	Q ² predict	Conclusion
Online Impulse Buying	0.612	Has a Predict Relevance
Positive Emotion	0.638	Has a Predict Relevance
Post-Purchased Dissonance	0.569	Has a Predict Relevance

Source: Result of Data Processing (2023).

Table 9 shows that the Q² predictive relevance value for the endogenous latent variable, i.e., Online Impulse Buying, is 0.612. Then, the Q² value of Positive Emotion is 0.638 and 0.569 for Post-purchased Dissonance. The Q² predictive relevance values for three endogenous latent variables are > 0, concluding that the model meets the criteria for good predictive relevance.

Next, the Goodness of Fit test aims to evaluate the measurement and structural models and provide a simple measurement of the overall model predictions (overall fit index). GoF consists of three criteria, i.e., 0.1 (small GoF), 0.25 (moderate GoF), and 0.36 (large GoF).

The following are the results of GoF calculations using the formula:

$$GoF = \sqrt{AVE \times R^2}$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{0,664 \times 0,623} = 0,643 \quad (2)$$

Based on the equation calculation, the GoF value is 0.643, included in the large GoF criteria value. It indicates that the measurement and structural models in this study are feasible and strong for prediction.

After comparing the outer model and inner model, the researchers assessed the hypothesis and its significance. The hypothesis and significance test findings are listed below:

Table 10: Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	T Statistic	P Value	F Square	Result
H1	0.137	2.142	0.016	0.023	Accepted
H2	0.278	2.561	0.005	0.066	Accepted
H3	0.198	2.281	0.011	0.043	Accepted
H4	0.296	2.765	0.003	0.190	Accepted
H5	0.747	20.342	0.000	1.259	Accepted

Source: Result of Data Processing (2023).

During the hypothesis testing process, two criteria must be met: t-statistics values > 1.65 for one-tailed hypotheses and p-values < 0.05. The purpose of comparing t-statistics values is to see the direction of influence and the significance level between variables. Meanwhile, the p-value is used to determine whether the hypothesis is accepted or rejected (Ali et al., 2019). Based on Table 8, the sales promotion and impulse buying variables have a t-value of 2,142 > 1.65 with a p-value of 0.016 < 0.05 and a path coefficient value of 0.137. It shows that sales

promotion has a positive and significant influence on the online impulse buying variable. The more attractive the advertising and promotions of the TikTok Shop, the more it encourages consumers to make purchases, especially unplanned purchases. It occurs due to the presence of cashback, bundling packages, or free shipping vouchers, making consumers believe they are benefiting when buying the products. Thus, it triggers consumers to buy more than what was previously planned, especially for consumers preferring shopping activities. Sales promotion is a variable with the smallest influence on impulse buying by 0.023.

The test results show that the relationship between the shopping lifestyle and impulse buying variables has a t-value of $2,561 > 1.65$ with a p-value of $0.005 < 0.05$ and a path coefficient value of 0.278. It indicates that shopping lifestyle positively and significantly influenced the online impulse buying variable. The higher the shopping lifestyle a customer has, the greater their urge to make impulse purchases. Hence, customers who like to spend their time shopping are more likely to make impulse purchases. Shopping lifestyle has a small influence on impulse buying by 0.066.

The social factor and impulse buying variables have a t-value of $2,281 > 1.65$ with a p-value of $0.011 < 0.05$ and a path coefficient value of 0.198. It shows that social factors have a positive and significant influence on the online impulse buying variable. The higher the encouragement and persuasion from people around you such as family members, friends, or reference groups, the higher the possibility of purchases. The influence value given is included in the small category by 0.043.

The positive emotion and impulse buying variables have a t-value of $2,765 > 1.65$ with a p-value of $0.003 < 0.05$ and a path coefficient value of 0.296. It means that positive emotion has a positive and significant influence on the online impulse buying variable. The more positive the emotions felt by consumers when shopping, especially at TikTok Shop, the more likely consumers will make impulse purchases. Positive emotion has a moderate influence on impulse buying by 0.190.

Furthermore, based on the test results, the relationship between online impulse buying and post-purchased dissonance has a t-value of 20,342 with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a path coefficient value of 0.747. It indicates that online impulse buying has a positive and significant influence on the post-purchased dissonance variable. The higher the level of impulse purchases on the TikTok Shop, the higher the post-purchase dissonance felt by consumers. Impulse buying has a big influence on post-purchase dissonance by 1.259.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Based on the study results, all hypotheses are accepted, where (1) Sales Promotion positively and significantly influences Online Impulse Buying on TikTok Shop, (2) Shopping Positively and significantly influences online Impulse Buying on TikTok Shop, (3) Shopping Lifestyle positively and significantly influences Online Impulse Buying on TikTok Shop, and (4) Positive Emotion positively and significantly influences Online Impulse Buying on TikTok Shop. The most affecting variable is positive emotion with an effect value of 0.190. Meanwhile,

sales promotion has the least effect on online impulse buying by 0.023. Another hypothesis is that (5) online impulse buying positively and significantly influences post-purchased dissonance on TikTok Shop. Based on the f-square value, online impulse buying significantly affects post-purchased dissonance by 1.259.

Based on the conclusion above, impulsive online purchasing decisions are influenced by mood, price, and social factors. Therefore, in encouraging impulse purchases, social commerce, especially TikTok Shop, can optimize the existing shop entertainment concept to create a sense of entertainment in consumers by continuing to present the latest trends or challenges that can inspire sellers to promote their sales in an interesting and creative way possible. Concerning price, TikTok Shop can also offer various sales promotions to its consumers more often.

Meanwhile, from social environmental factors, it is recommended that TikTok Shop collaborate more with various parties such as the influencer community, online shop community, and other parties to using the TikTok platform more often to sell, considering that consumers' intense interaction with their social environment has been proven to create an urge to buy products and create online impulse buying.

The study findings also show that online impulsivity causes post-purchase dissonance on online consumers, especially TikTok Shop. Therefore, to overcome these negative emotions at the start of a purchase, companies can introduce incentives such as coupons for future purchases. The company can also review the return policy to make it more flexible to reduce the inconvenience experienced by some consumers after receiving the product. Then, it is recommended that further research can add other factors that can influence consumer involvement in impulsive purchases such as payment methods or hedonic shopping. Future studies can also discuss other impacts of the impulse buying variable on consumers. For example, satisfaction or brand switching.

References

- 1) Ahmad, S. H., Wolok, T. and Abdussamad, Z. K. (2022) 'Pengaruh Shopping Lifestyle Dan Promosi Produk Skin Care Terhadap Impulse Buying Melalui Media Tiktok Shop', *JAMBURA: Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen dan Bisnis*, 5(2), pp. 784–793. Available at: <https://ejournal.ung.ac.id/index.php/JIMB/article/view/16550>.
- 2) Antara, I. M. R. S. and Rastini, N. M. (2022) 'The Influence of Brand Image, Sales Promotion and Quality of Service on Customer Satisfaction Car Rental Service', *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 7(2), pp. 223–226. doi: 10.24018/ejbmr.2022.7.2.1273.
- 3) Aprilia, R. S., Indrawati and Rachmawati, I. (2022) 'The effect of hedonic shopping motivation and sales promotion on impulse buying through positive emotion as intervening variables on the marketplace shopee', *Sustainable Future: Trends, Strategies and Development*, pp. 26–28. doi: 10.1201/9781003335832-7.
- 4) Aqmala, D. and Putra, F. I. F. S. (2022) 'Ask, Bid, Buy! Online Impulse Buying Behaviour of Ethnic Chinese Mothers in Indonesia', *Quality - Access to Success*, 23(190), pp. 342–354. doi: 10.47750/QAS/23.190.36.
- 5) Bandyopadhyay, N. *et al.* (2021) 'Immediate or delayed! Whether various types of consumer sales promotions drive impulse buying?: An empirical investigation', *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 61(January), p. 102532. doi: 10.1016/j.jretconser.2021.102532.

- 6) Barta, S., Gurrea, R. and Flavián, C. (2022) ‘The role of flow consciousness in consumer regret’, *Internet Research*, 32(3), pp. 875–896. doi: 10.1108/INTR-08-2020-0482.
- 7) Betty, J., Alm, J. and McKee, M. (2006) ‘Audit Information Dissemination, Taxpayer Communication, and Compliance Behavior’, *SSRN Electronic Journal*, (May 2018). doi: 10.2139/ssrn.897348.
- 8) Blattberg, R. C. and Neslin, S. A. (1993) ‘Sales Promotion Models’, *Handbooks in Operations Research and Management Science*, 5(C), pp. 553–609. doi: 10.1016/S0927-0507(05)80035-0.
- 9) Chan, K. H. C. *et al.* (2017) ‘The state of online impulse buying research : A literature analysis’, *Information & Management*, 54, pp. 204–217.
- 10) Chen *et al.* (2020) ‘Understanding Consumers’ Post-Purchase Dissonance by Online Impulse Buying-Beauty Product’, in *ICMECG '20: Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Management of e-Commerce and e-Government*. Jeju Island: ACM Digital Library.
- 11) Chen, W. K., Chen, C. W. and Lin, Y. C. (2020) ‘Understanding the influence of impulse buying toward consumers’ post-purchase dissonance and return intention: an empirical investigation of apparel websites’, *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, (0123456789). doi: 10.1007/s12652-020-02333-z.
- 12) Chetioui, Y. and El Bouzidi, L. (2023) ‘An investigation of the nexus between online impulsive buying and cognitive dissonance among Gen Z shoppers: Are female shoppers different?’, *Young Consumers*, (December 2022). doi: 10.1108/YC-06-2022-1548.
- 13) Cnnindonesia.com (2022) *Dilema Beli Produk di Medsos karena Terpengaruh ‘Influencer’*, *CNN Indonesia*.
- 14) Databoks (2022) *Pendapatan TikTok Tembus US\$1,6 Miliar pada Kuartal II 2022*, *databoks.katadata.co.id*.
- 15) Evans, O. (2019) ‘Repositioning for Increased Digital Dividends: Internet Usage and Economic Well-being in Sub-Saharan Africa’, *Journal of Global Information Technology Management*, 22(1), pp. 47–70. doi: 10.1080/1097198X.2019.1567218.
- 16) Fu, S., Yan, Q. and Feng, G. C. (2018) ‘Who will attract you? Similarity effect among users on online purchase intention of movie tickets in the social shopping context’, *International Journal of Information Management*, 40(January), pp. 88–102. doi: 10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2018.01.013.
- 17) Ghozali, I. (2021) *Partial Least Squares Konsep, Teknik, dan Aplikasi Menggunakan Program SmartPLS 3.2.9 Untuk Penelitian Empiris*. 3rd edn. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- 18) Ghozali, I. and Latan, H. (2017) *Partial Least Square: Konsep, Metode, dan Aplikasi menggunakan program WarpPLS 5.0*. Edisi ke-3. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- 19) Hair Jr., J. F. *et al.* (2021) *Review of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) Using R: A Workbook*, *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*. doi: 10.1080/10705511.2022.2108813.
- 20) Hajjat, F. M. (2021) ‘Using marketing for good: An experiential project on cause-related marketing in a principles course’, *Journal of Education for Business*, 96(7), pp. 461–467. doi: 10.1080/08832323.2020.1848770.
- 21) Hamid, R. S. and Anwar, S. (2017) *Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)*. Edisi 1. Edited by Abiratno, N. Sofa, and D. A. D. Raksanagara. DKI Jakarta: PT Inkubator Penulis Indonesia.
- 22) Hasan Usma, D. R. N. (2014) ‘The Empirical Study of Relationship between Post Purchase Dissonance and Consumer Behaviour Uzma Hasan 1 and Dr. Reshma Nasreen 2’, *Journal of Marketing Management*, 2(2), pp. 65–77.

- 23) He, H., Kukar-Kinney, M. and Ridgway, N. M. (2018) 'Compulsive buying in China: Measurement, prevalence, and online drivers', *Journal of Business Research*, 91(71302108), pp. 28–39. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.05.023.
- 24) Hikmawati, F. (2017) *Metodologi Penelitian*. Depok: PT RajaGrafindo Persada.
- 25) Japarianto, E. and Sugiharto, S. (2011) 'Pengaruh Shopping Life Style Dan Fashion Involvement Terhadap Impulse Buying Behavior Masyarakat High Income Surabaya', *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran*, 6(1), pp. 32–41.
- 26) Kompas.com (2023) *TikTok Shop Makin Digemari Warganet di Asia Tenggara untuk Belanja Online*, *tekno.kompas.com*.
- 27) Kotler and Keller, K. L. (2021) *Marketing Management 16th Ed*. Pearson.
- 28) Kumar, A. *et al.* (2020) 'Impulse Buying and Post-Purchase Regret: a Study of Shopping Behaviour for the Purchase of Grocery Products', *International Journal of Management*, 11(12), pp. 614–624. doi: 10.34218/ijm.11.12.2020.057.
- 29) Lazim, N. A. M. *et al.* (2020) 'Measuring Post-purchase Regret and Impulse Buying in Online Shopping Experience from Cognitive Dissonance Theory Perspective', *2020 6th IEEE International Conference on Information Management, ICIM 2020*, pp. 7–13. doi: 10.1109/ICIM49319.2020.244662.
- 30) Liputan6.com (2021) *71 Persen Pengguna Tertarik Membeli Produk Setelah Lihat Video Review TikTok*, *Liputan6.com*.
- 31) Made, D. and Purnama, F. (2019) 'Hedonic Shopping Motivation , Shopping Lifestyle , Price Reduction toward Impulse Buying Behavior in Shopping Center', 3, pp. 48–54.
- 32) Martaleni, M. *et al.* (2022) 'Flash sale and online impulse buying: Mediation effect of emotions', *Innovative Marketing*, 18(2), pp. 49–59. doi: 10.21511/im.18(2).2022.05.
- 33) Novia, D. N. (2020) *Hubungan Pembelian Impulsif dengan Penyesalam Pasca Pembelian Online pada Mahasiswi Psikologi Universitas Medan Area*.
- 34) Octavilia, D. (2023) *Penjualan TikTok Shop Melebihi Marketplace Tokopedia. Cek Faktanya*, *pop-star.me*.
- 35) Pujiastuti, N., Reza, R. and Astuti, R. F. (2022) 'Pengaruh literasi ekonomi dan lingkungan sosial terhadap perilaku pembelian impulsif pada mahasiswa', *Jurnal Riset Pendidikan Ekonomi*, 7(1), pp. 107–117. doi: 10.21067/jrpe.v7i1.6710.
- 36) Raji, R. A., Rashid, S. and Ishak, S. (2019) 'The mediating effect of brand image on the relationships between social media advertising content, sales promotion content and behavioural intention', *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 13(3), pp. 302–330. doi: 10.1108/JRIM-01-2018-0004.
- 37) Sameeni, M. S., Ahmad, W. and Filieri, R. (2022) 'Brand betrayal, post-purchase regret, and consumer responses to hedonic versus utilitarian products: The moderating role of betrayal discovery mode', *Journal of Business Research*, 141(December 2021), pp. 137–150. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.12.019.
- 38) Sari, N. Y. And Hermawati, S. (2020) 'The Effect Of Shopping Lifestyle , Hedonic Shopping Motivation , And Sales Promotion On Impulse Buying Behavior In E-Commerce (Case Study Of Berrybenka Consumer)', Pp. 45–54.
- 39) Shaifali, C., Vishal, D. and Richa, B. (2021) 'Analysis of Impulse Buying Behaviour of Consumer During COVID-19: An Empirical Study.pdf', *Millennial Asia*. doi: 10.1177/09763996211041215.
- 40) Shan, Y., Chen, K. J. and Lin, J. S. (2020) 'When social media influencers endorse brands: the effects of self-influencer congruence, parasocial identification, and perceived endorser motive', *International Journal of Advertising*, 39(5), pp. 590–610. doi: 10.1080/02650487.2019.1678322.

- 41) Soodan, V. and Pandey, A. C. (2016) 'Influence of Emotions on Consumer Behaviour: A Study on FMCG Purchases in Uttarkhand, India', *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Business and Economics*, 4(2), pp. 163–181.
- 42) Stern, H. (1962) 'The Significance of Impulse Buying Today', *Journal of Marketing*, 26(2). doi: 10.1177/002224296202600212.
- 43) Sudarsono, J. G. (2017) 'Pengaruh Visual Merchandising Terhadap Impulse Buying Melalui Positive Emotion Pada Zara Surabaya', *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran*, 11(1), pp. 16–25. doi: 10.9744/pemasaran.11.1.16-25.
- 44) Suyanto, A. and Femi, S. R. (2023) 'Analysis of The Effect of Impulsive Purchase and Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in Beauty E-Commerce', *Quality - Access to Success*, 24(194), pp. 18–23. doi: 10.47750/QAS/24.194.03.
- 45) Tran, T.-T. (2019) 'Factors affecting the impulse shopping intention of Vietnamese people: An application case in Ho Chi Minh City', *International Journal of Advanced And Applied Sciences*, 6(2), pp. 65–74. doi: 10.21833/ijaas.2019.02.010.
- 46) Zheng, Y. *et al.* (2020) 'Perceived stress and online compulsive buying among women: A moderated mediation model', *Computers in Human Behavior*, 103(September 2019), pp. 13–20. doi: 10.1016/j.chb.2019.09.012.